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Comparative Analysis between Teacher's Competency and Performance in Economics among Secondary School Students in Ika South, Delta State, Nigeria

Onyechi, Kingsley Abaye

Email: onyechiabaye@gmail.com

Tel: 08066400403

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria

Abstract

This study examines the comparative analysis of teachers' competency and its impact on the performance of economics students and adopts a descriptive design. It employs a multi-stage sampling procedure. This procedure was used to select one hundred and ninety-eight (198) participants which consists of 180 SSII students and 18 teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta state. The research investigates the relationship between teachers' subject knowledge, instructional strategies, and professional qualifications with students' academic outcomes in economics. Teachers' Competence Scale (TCS) and Economics Achievement Test (EAT) were used to elicit data for the study reliability coefficient of 0.87 and 0.81 were obtained respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The data were analysed using the Pearson "r" statistic, t-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings reveal that teachers with higher levels of subject-specific skill and effective pedagogical skills consistently foster better academic performance among students. In addition, professional development initiatives and competency-building programs were found to have a significant influence on bridging performance gaps. The study emphasizes the critical role of teacher competency in shaping student success and provides recommendations for improving teacher training programs, attending conferences, seminars and workshops of stakeholders in education to enhance students' academic performance to enhance students' academic outcomes in economics education.

Keywords: Competency, Qualifications, Experience, Economics and Performance.

Introduction

The subject Economics appears to be one of the electives subjects in secondary schools and compulsory subjects for all commercial students at the senior secondary school (SSS) level under the new National policy on Education. According to Ogbebor (2013) Economics is a subject that deals with the principle and practice of undertaking everyday activities that engender the well-being of the individual, society and the nation at large. This implies that with the study of Economics, individuals can survive because they are able to acquire basic knowledge and skills that will enable them to better appreciate the nature of economic problems in any society. Furthermore, Economics as a subject provides training for students on how to make rational use of scarce resources to satisfy their unlimited wants, to build up theories and tools for economic analysis, provide rationale guide to firms and governments in allocating scarce resources, to understand and appreciate economic problems facing the society and suggest ways of rectifying them (Fehintola & Yahya, 2019).

According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2012) Economics exposes students to basic economic problems of the society and a better understanding of man's economic activities and how to solve them for better living in the society. The major goal of the teaching and learning of Economics, as stipulated in the Economics curriculum, according to the Federal Ministry of Education (2012) is to equip graduands of senior secondary school students with basic knowledge and skills to appreciate the nature of Economic problems in any society and adequately prepare them for the challenges in the Nigerian Economy. Therefore, it becomes necessary that students should achieve highly in Economics test and examinations to enable take a good decision and manage their resources very well. Academic achievement is regarded as students' score or grade in a test or an examination. Okonkwo (2016) stated that academic achievement is a scholastic position of a student at any given time. Achievement is a construct that is measurable using standardized series of tests, usually developed for school subjects by examination bodies and ministries of education such as West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO).

In spite of the importance of this subject to the society and the contributions made by successive government and critical stakeholders, the performance of students in Economics Examinations and Test appears to be decreasing. The WAEC Chief examiner's report (2022) on economics subject noted that the persistent decrease in the performance of Economics students in senior secondary certificate examination leaves no doubt about the competency and motivation of Economics teachers in schools. Others include large class size, inadequate and un-conducive classrooms for teaching and learning Economics, in adequate Economics text books for learning process, insufficient qualified Economics teachers to

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reduce the work load of the teachers, inadequate time to Economics subjects by student and inadequate incentives to the Economics teachers to make them dedicated to their teaching profession. (Omotegbona, 2020).

The implication is that it could lead to poor academic performance among senior secondary school student. Therefore, to improve the performance of students in Economics, government and employers of labour need to focus on quality education. The world of education must also be supported by competent, reliable and quality human resources to realize quality or superior education at all levels of society. Teacher competence refers to the ability of educators to effectively carry out their responsibilities in alignment with educational objectives (Bamidele, 2024). The competence of teachers is fundamental for quality instruction and student academic performance. (Pascoe et al., 2020). Research indicates that a teacher's understanding of the subject matter significantly affects both the content taught and the methods used, ultimately influencing student outcomes. This relationship between subject knowledge and pedagogy encompasses classroom management, lesson structure, and teaching strategies (Bamidele, 2024).

According to Akiri & Ugborugbo (2009) a teacher's competence is regarded as a multidimensional construct, which encompasses numerous interconnected elements towards the transformation of knowledge to learners. Meziobi & Meziobi (2012) describe teachers' competence as demonstrable, professionally acquired, specified requisite teaching skills, abilities, and attitudes essential for effective teaching. The authors further stress that the possession of a repertoire of these prerequisite teaching skills and attitudes spans beyond the three domains of learning and, therefore, may not be restricted only to them. Thus, a teacher can be competent in the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective areas of the instructional process. In line with this, Uchefuna (2010) noted that teaching and learning depend on teachers' competence, consequently, a competent teacher could be conceptualized as one who produces desired results in psychomotor, cognitive, and affective domains of education. Teachers' competence involves all aspects of teachers' abilities that could influence the teaching and learning process being geared towards attaining the desirable set objectives of Economics in secondary schools.

To be a competent Economics teacher, the teacher needs to possess required qualification such as degree in Economics Education with wealth of experience in teaching the subject (Economics) and mastery of subject matter. Teacher's qualification refers to the kind of professional education for teaching that the teacher has received (Agbor, Onnoghen, & Etan, 2023). Qualification relates to the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills, competence and creativity needed for quality productive engagement in the teaching profession. A teacher's academic qualification is the educational attainments of the teacher. A teacher academic certification is a combined set of qualifications which include general academic and verbal ability, subject matter knowledge and teacher education (Yakubu, 2023). Academically, qualified teachers are referred to those who have academic training as a result of enrolment into educational institution and obtained qualifications such as B.Sc.Ed Economics while professionally qualified teachers are those who got professional training that gave them professional knowledge, skill, techniques, aptitudes as different from the general education (Edu and Kalu, 2012). It appears that student's performance is enhanced when taught with high qualified teachers than when taught with less qualified. A qualified teacher has the capacity to teach and improve on students' learning thereby leading to high academic performance. Segun (2016) confirmed that for any meaningful teaching and learning to take place, teacher qualification needs to be very high. Macaulay (2016) affirmed the above assertion by Segun (2016) qualifications must relate to academic and professional preparation, professional growth, classroom interaction and evaluation. This is true because a lecturer who is not trained in a particular discipline will not perform as much as if he trained in that particular field. In this case the lecturer relies on 'reading and teaching' because the in-depth knowledge is lacking for effective instructional

According to Gibbons, as cited in Agharuwhe (2013) students who are taught by more experienced teachers perform better academically because these teachers are more adept at both teaching the subject matter and dealing with a variety of classroom issues. The effectiveness of a teacher increases systematically with increase in number of years of teaching. Teachers' experiences can therefore either improve or lower students' academic achievement. By implication, teachers with less years of experience have a lower academic accomplishment rate than those with more. Papay & Kraff (2014) stated that inexperienced teachers are teachers with few years into the teaching profession trying to survive in the classroom because they are building key classroom management skills, learning the curriculum and adding to their instructional skills.

It is essential for an efficient, professional and competent teacher to possess a good knowledge of subject matter. Mastery of subject matter refers to the level at which the teacher possesses a good grasp of knowledge of the subject he teaches and skills necessary for teaching the subject (Ntibi, Neji, & Agube, 2020). Teachers without good grasp of subject matter, can succeed in bluffing the students and imparting incorrect information which is likely to bring difficulties to the learners and to other teachers who teach the learners. Mezieobi (2012) stated that teacher must possess sufficient knowledge in their area of teaching. Any teacher that does not possess the required knowledge of subject matter in his area of teaching cannot be effective. That includes how well the teacher masters the subject matter, lesson preparation and presentation, punctuality

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and attendance to class, clear communication efficacy in students' evaluation, and engendering effectiveness concerning the outcome. Teachers of Economics need not just be competent but require motivation for effective teaching and learning of the subject.

Theoretical Framework

Competence motivation Theory: Competence motivation theory (CMT) is a motivational framework forwarded by Susan Harter (1978, 1981) for understanding achievement- related behaviour in various domains (e.g., academics, social, physical). Harter's theory expanded on the seminal work of White (1959), This theory explains why people are motivated to participate in activities where they feel competent. It suggests that people are driven to develop or demonstrate their skills, and that success in a particular domain can lead to increased competence motivation. According to the theory competence motivation increases when a person successfully masters a task. This encourages the person to master more tasks. Success in that domain will help them recognize that they can control their performance. High perceptions of competence and control create feelings of pleasure that maintain or lead to an increase in competence motivation. It is useful to the students who are successful when attempting new skills or tasks and receive positive reinforcement will internalize a self-reward system as well as a set of mastery goals. This can have a positive and long-term effect on their confidence. Because they are internalizing their own set of standards, students will no longer be dependent on others to evaluate their performances or motivate them to continue. Instead, they will be motivated to continue on their own because they recognize they are competent in that area. More importantly, it will also give the teachers to put in their best and applied the best methods to teach the students using teachers- students centred methods of teaching. On the part of Economics students, their performance and interest in studying Economics will be high because of the quality of Economics teachers teaching the students with wealth of experience.

Empirical Review

Teachers Competency and Students Academic Performance

Bamidele (2024) examines the relationship between teacher competence and the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Utilising a descriptive survey design, data were collected from 203 secondary schools, focusing on teacher competencies such as mastery of subject matter, teaching qualifications, teaching experience, training, and regular supervision. The findings revealed that out of 1118 respondents in the 2014/2015 session, 64.67% achieved 5 credits and above, including Mathematics and English. A significant positive correlation was observed between teacher competence and students' academic performance, with r-cal value of 0.770 indicating that higher teacher competence is associated with improved student outcomes. Specifically, mastery of subject matter and teaching qualifications were identified as the most impactful variables.

Idika & Onuoha (2018) investigated the influence of Economics teachers' personality on students' classroom performance in Public Secondary Schools in Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted Ex-post facto research design. The sample consisted of 19 teachers randomly selected out of thirty-one and their SS2 Economics students numbering 326. An observational schedule titled Economics teachers' personality test (ETP) was the instrument for data collection. The academic records (grades) of the students were collected from the 19 teachers. One research question was answered using mean and standard deviation and four null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance using t- test and ANOVA. The findings revealed that teachers' gender had no effect on the classroom performance of the students. However, teachers teaching experience, qualifications, interpersonal relationship with students, knowledge of subject matter, and attitude of the teacher had influence on students' classroom performance.

Nwankwo (2021) examined teachers' competence, motivation as correlates of senior secondary school students' academic achievement in economics in Imo State. The study adopted a linear correlation design. The population of the study was 94,963 Senior Secondary School Students (SS1-SS3) from 275 public secondary schools in Imo State. A sample of 500 SS2 Economics students was involved in the study. Purposive and random sampling techniques were used. The research instruments for this study are the Teachers' Competence Scale (TCS), Teachers' Motivation Scale (TMS), and Economics Achievement Test (EAT). The data were analyzed using the Pearson "r" statistic for research questions 1 and 2, while multiple linear regression statistics were used for research question 3. Hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using t-test significance of correlation and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypothesis 3 at 5% level of significance. The result showed that there is a highly significant relationship between teachers' competence, motivation, and students' academic achievement in Economics.

Annas, Istiqomah & Ika (2019) measured the effect of teacher competencies on student learning outcomes. The research sample consisted of 60 teachers and 60 students at Muhammadiyah Bambanglipuro Vocational High School, Bantul, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. The data was collected through a questionnaire method. The collected data were analyzed using simple regression with SPSS. It showed the determination result of the independent variable that the determination coefficient showed the direct effect of the teacher ss proficiencies variable on learning outcomes stated in percentages. In

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this case, the calculated result is 0,084. It means that the teacher competencies variable directly affects the student learning outcome variable by 8,4%, while the (100% -8,4%) 91,6% is influenced by other factors beyond the teacher competencies variable.

Teachers Years of Teaching Experience and Students Academic Performance

Okose & Obiunu (2024) investigated Influence of Teachers' years of Teaching Experience and Qualification on Students' Academic Performance in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science. The study which was carried out in the three senatorial district of Delta State was guided by two specific objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses. Ex-Post facto research design was adopted. The sample comprised of ninety Junior Secondary III Basic science teachers and 1800 students who sat for the Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science in the 2021/2022 academic session. Data were collected through the multistage sampling procedure. Basic Science Teachers' Questionnaire (BSTQ) was use elicit the teacher's information and the Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science was used to access the student's performance. Research question was answered using mean and standard deviation while the t-test analysis was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that teachers' years of teaching experience and qualification has influence on the mean academic performance of Basic science students in BECE.

Ene et.al (2022) examined Influence of Teachers' years of Teaching Experience on Students' Academic Achievement in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science. The study which was carried out in Nsukka Education zone was guided by one specific purpose, one research question and one null hypothesis. Ex-Post facto research design was adopted. The population comprised 4,195 Junior Secondary III Basic science teachers and students in Nsukka Education Zone. The sample consisted of 365 respondents, and was determined using multistage sampling procedure. Basic Science Teachers' Questionnaire (BSTQ) and Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) were the instruments and were validated by experts in the department of Science Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Research question was answered using mean and standard deviation while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study showed that teachers' years of teaching experience has influence on the mean academic achievement of Basic science students in BECE.

Teachers Qualification and Students Academic performance

Agbor, Onnoghen & Etan (2023) explored the relationship between teachers' qualification and students' academic performance in Environmental Education in University of Calabar. The research design adopted for the study was survey research design. Two research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide to study. The population of the study consisted of 672 undergraduate students from Department of Environmental Education. A sample of 134 students was used for the study, this constituted 20% of the population. A structured questionnaire title: Teachers' Qualification and Environmental Education Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (TQEESAPQ). Pearson products moment correlation coefficient analysis was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Findings in the study revealed that teachers with environmental education qualification positively relate with students' academic performance.

Onuegbu (2023) investigated the effects of teachers' qualification on students' academic performance in private secondary schools in Southeastern Nigeria. Through a thoughtfully designed survey, over 515 respondents from 187 schools shared insights into their daily educational realities. Their responses revealed generally qualified teaching staff dedicated to covering subjects comprehensively.

Teachers Mastery of Subject Matter and Students Academic Performance

Ntibi, Neji & Agube (2020) examined the influence of students' perception of teacher knowledge of subject matter/ lesson presentation and academic achievement in Physics in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. Two hypotheses were formulated to direct the study and literature was reviewed on the variables under study. Ex-post facto design research was adopted for the study. A total sample of 50 Physics students were selected using simple random sampling procedure. The questionnaire and Physics Achievement Test (PAT) were the main instruments used for data collection. The reliability estimate of the instrument was established through Cronbach Alpha reliability and Kudar-Richarson's formular (KR-21) which yielded an estimate of .83 and .81 respectively. One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistic was adopted to test the two hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis revealed that there is a significant influence of students' perception of teacher knowledge of subject matter and academic achievement in Physics. Secondly, finding revealed that mode of lesson presentation has significant influence on students' academic performance in Physics.

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Sadiq (2019) examined the relationship between teacher's knowledge of subject matter and students' academic achievements in economics in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The study was set to achieve certain objectives, research questions and hypotheses, the researcher adopted this study will adopt a descriptive survey design; the area of the study is Adamawa State. The population of the study is 5465 comprising of 337 principals 5128 teachers in all the public secondary schools within the five education zones of Adamawa state. The sample size of 73 principals and 372 teachers in both selected zone is determined by Taro Yamane formula for finite population from the selected zones. The instrument was questionnaire on teacher's knowledge of subject matter and a proforma for student academic achievement results from selected schools from 2015-2018 WASSCE that is WAEC results. The instrument was validated by four Senior Lecturers. A reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha Method. The data was collected through the administration of the questionnaires. The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. While inferential statistics such as multiple correlations were used to test the null hypothesis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. the result of the finding revealed that hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance was rejected and was concluded that teachers' knowledge of the subject matter contributed to secondary school students' academic achievement in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Statement of the Research Problem

The competency of teachers plays a vital role in shaping students' academic performance and overall development. In spite of substantial investments in teacher training and education systems, significant disparities in student achievement persist. Factors such as teachers' subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, classroom management, and ability to address diverse learning needs directly influence students' outcomes. However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding of how specific teacher competencies correlate with student performance across various contexts. This gap in knowledge hinders the development of targeted interventions to enhance teaching effectiveness and student success. Addressing this issue is critical to improving educational quality and equity, ensuring all students have access to competent and effective teachers who can meet their diverse learning needs.

Objective of the study

Specifically, the study sets out to achieve the following objectives:

1. To examine the relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. To determine the influence of teachers' educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.
3. To determine the influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. How does teachers' educational qualifications influence the academic performance of Economics students.
3. To what extent do teachers' years of teaching experience influence the academic performance of Economics students.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between students' academic performance in Economics and teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics
2. There is no significant influence of teachers' educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.
3. There is no significant influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design is use for this study. The population for this study comprises all the male and the female SSII senior secondary school students offering Economics and Economics teachers in Ika South local government of Delta state. There are seven public senior secondary schools in Ika South local government of Delta State in 2022/2023 academic session. This population is considered appropriate because they are free from external examination such as WAEC and NECO. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select one-hundred and ninety-eight (198) participants which consists of 180 students and 18 teachers. The sample also consists of 104 females and 94 males. In selecting the students, simple random sampling was used to select One hundred and eighty (180) students from six selected senior secondary schools. That is thirty (30) students each from the six (6) selected senior secondary schools using lucky dip method. That is asking

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the students to pick a paper written “Yes or No” from the box. The participants that pick “YES” is automatically selected for the study while those that pick “No” were not selected. Convenient sampling was used to select eighteen (18) teachers. For data collection, the study made use of two rating scales titled Teachers’ Competence Scale (TCS) and Teachers’ Motivation Scale (TMS) and an achievement test titled Economics Achievement Test (EAT). Teachers’ Competence Scale (TCS) has 15 items with 3 sub-scale namely Teachers Qualification, Teachers Teaching Experience and Teachers Subject Matter. The scale was prepared in terms of four response options of strongly agree=4points, agree=3points, disagree=2points, and strongly disagree=1point. The achievement test has 20 item questions in 4 multiple choice forms adapted from 4 subtopics in the Economics Syllabus to get information on the academic achievement of the students. Draft copies of the scales were given to three specialists from the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation and Economics for face validation, but the achievement test was subjected to content, validity using a table of specifications. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability of Teachers Competent Scale and Economics Achievement Test (EAT) with reliability coefficient of 0.87 and 0.81 respectively. The statistical tools used were the t-test, Pearson product moment correlation and analysis of variance. The study hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

The result was presented in tables in line with the purpose of study and the corresponding null hypothesis that guided the study.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students’ academic performance in Economics.

Table 1: The Relationship between Teachers Knowledge of subject matter and Students Academic performance test

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	r-cal	r-critic	Decision
1	Economics Test	180	16.38	1.69	0.650	0.1593	Significant
2	Teachers Knowledge of subject matter	18	18.05	0.93			

Table 1 above shows that the mean and scores of Economics students was 16.38 and 1.69 while that of Teachers’ knowledge of the subject matter in Economic was 18.05 and 0.93 respectively. Table 1 also showed that the r-calculated value of 0.650 is greater than t critical value of 0.1593. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value the null hypothesis is reject. This means there is significant relation between Teachers’ possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students’ academic performance in Economics.

Ho₂: There is no significant influence of teachers’ educational qualifications on academic performance of Economics students.

Table 2: t-test difference between Economics’ Teachers educational qualification Students’ Academic performance

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std Dev	Df	t-cal	t-critic	Decision
1	Economics Teachers with Master degree in Econs Edu	4	18.00	0.81	16	2.239	1.976	Significant
2	Economics Teachers with Bachelor degree in Econs Edu	14	16.07	1.63				

Table 2 above shows that the mean and standard deviation scores of Economics teachers with Master degrees in Education was 18.00 and 0.81 while that of Economics Teachers with Bachelor degree in Economics Education was 16.07 and 1.63 respectively. Table 2 also showed that the t-calculated value of 2.239 is greater than t critical value of 1.976. Since the t-calculated value is greater than the t-critical value the null hypothesis is reject. Hence, there is significant influence of teachers’ qualification on student academic performance in Economics.

Ho₃: There is no significant influence of teachers’ years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students.

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Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Influence of Teachers' Years of Teaching Experience on the Mean Academic Performance Scores of Economics Students

S/N	Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	4	14.2500	1.70783	Significant
2	6 YEARS -10 years	6	16.8333	.98319	
3	11 years and above	8	17.3750	1.06066	
	Total	18	16.5000	1.68907	

Result in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of academic performance scores of Economics students in Test by teachers' years of teaching experience. Result shows that students who were taught by teachers with 1-5 years of teaching experience had mean of 14.25 with a standard deviation of 1.70. Students taught by teachers with 6-10 years of teaching experience had a mean score of 16.83 with a standard deviation of 0.98. Also, students taught by teachers with 11 years and above with teaching experience had mean score of 17.37 with a standard deviation of 1.06. The result of the study shows that as teachers' years of teaching experience increases, students' academic achievement also increases. The overall means score of 16.50 was obtained with a standard deviation of 1.68. This result shows that teachers' years of teaching experience has influence on the mean academic achievement scores of Economics students. To determine whether there is significant difference exists in Economics performance Test scores among participants, one-way ANOVA was used and the results are presented in Table 4

Table 4: Showing ANOVA Summary Table on the Difference in the Mean Scores of Students In Economics and Teachers Years of experience

S/N	Variable	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Between Groups	27.042	2	13.521	9.451	.002	Significant
2	Within Groups	21.458	15	1.431			
	Total	48.500	17				

The ANOVA results presented in Table 4 shows that the F-value of 9.451 was greater than the F-critical value of 3.63, given 2 and 15 degrees of freedom at the .05 level of significance. Since the calculated F-value was greater than the F-critical value, hypothesis 3 was rejected which means that there is significant influence of teachers' years of teaching experience on academic performance of Economics students in Ika South local Government. This implies that teachers' years of teaching experience is a significant factor in determining students' achievement in Economics. To test for the direction of the difference, a post-test comparison of means was conducted and the result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Post Hoc Test of the Comparison between the means

S/N	(I) GROUP	(J) GROUP	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	6 YEARS -10 years	-2.58333*	.77205	.004
2		11 years and above	-3.12500*	.73243	.001
3	6 YEARS -10 years	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	2.58333*	.77205	.004
4		11 years and above	-.54167	.64595	.415
5	11 years and above	1-5 YEARS EXPERIENCE	3.12500*	.73243	.001
6		6 YEARS -10 years	.54167	.64595	.415

Table 5 shows a multiple comparison test of the variation in students' mean scores in the Economics test based on teachers' years of teaching experience. The outcome demonstrates that there was discernible difference in the mean score between students taught by teachers with 1-5 years of experience and those with 6-10 years of experience (2.58*). There was significant difference between students who were taught by teachers with "1-5 years" and "11 years above (3.12*). The finding also demonstrated that Economics students taught by teachers with 11 years above perform better than students taught by teachers with 6-10 years. Also, students taught by teachers with 6-10 years did better than students taught by teachers with 1-5 years.

Discussion of findings

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The result of this first hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between Teachers' possession of knowledge of the subject matter in Economics and students' academic performance in Economics. This finding agreed with Emeh and Agba, (2010) who ascertain that teachers' Mastery of subject matter has much influence on the process of achieving the lesson's objective. Also, in line with Chidi (2016) who in his study on the relationship between teachers' mastery of the subject matter and student academic achievement in simultaneous equations in Enugu State and agreed that there is a significant influence of teachers' mastery of the subject matter on students' academic achievement in Physics. The result of finding from hypothesis 2 showed a significant difference between teachers' educational qualifications and students' academic performance in Economics. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Macaulay (2016) who observed that qualifications relate to academic and professional preparation, professional growth, classroom interaction and evaluation, which in turn result in high academic performance. The result also corroborated the finding of Agbor, Onnoghen & Etan (2023) who find out that there is a significant relationship between teacher qualification and students' academic performance in Environmental Education in University of Calabar, Nigeria.

The result of the study in hypothesis 3 shows that teachers' years of teaching experience have significant influence on the mean academic achievement scores of Economics students This difference is in the direction of teachers with 6-10 years and 11 years and above in which these teachers perform better than other teachers below. The result is in accordance with Agharuwhe (2013) who stated that effectiveness due to number of years into teaching might positively influence students' academic achievement. The result of the study is consistent with Ewetan & Ewetan (2015) who found that teachers teaching experience has significantly influence students' academic achievement in mathematics and English language as measured by their achievement in SSCE and as perceived by the respondents. Schools that have more teachers with experience above ten years in teaching achieved better result than schools having more teachers with less than ten years teaching experience. The result also agrees with Bamidele & Adekola (2017) who found that there was significant difference in the achievement of students taught by long time experienced teachers and short time experienced teachers. Ene et.al (2022) highlighted that having more experienced teachers will result in pupils who do better. Okose & Obiunu (2024) discovered a correlation between teachers' teaching experience and students' academic achievement in Basic Education Certificate Examination in Basic Science, which is consistent with the outcome of this study.

Conclusion

Drawing from the results of this study, it can be said that when teachers employ teaching competency technology effectively, students' academic performance will increase, and they will be able to comprehend the subject matter better. Students who have a thorough comprehension of the subject matter will be able to score very well on external exams that consist of standardized test items, in addition to performing well on teacher-made assessments. In conclusion, investing in teachers' professional development and fostering a supportive educational environment are key strategies for improving student achievement. Properly implemented, it enhances learning and fosters a collaborative classroom.

Recommendations

On the basis of study finding the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should improve their competence of the subject matter through attending conferences, seminars and workshops of stakeholders in education to enhance students' academic achievement.
2. The experienced teachers should mentor the less experienced teachers, and capacity building programs should be organized.
3. All Economics teachers in senior secondary schools must possess at least B.sc and M.Ed in Economics education.

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